

The Arbeitsgemeinschaft Universitätsverlage (AG Universitätsverlage)¹ is an association of publishers and publication services from German-speaking countries that offer publishing services and have a proven connection to a research institution. Based on the “Quality Standards for Open Access Monographs and Anthologies” (2018)², the AG Universitätsverlage presents the following updated quality standards for Open Access (OA) books.³

Quality Standards for Open Access Books

Preamble

In order to guarantee Open Access to books in a reliable and sustainable quality, it is necessary to adhere to standards. The present quality standards refer to books in immediate Open Access (Gold OA, Diamond OA). Criteria that a publisher or publication service currently is unable to implement should be included in its development goals.

§ 1 Accessibility and Visibility

Summary

- Reliable and transparent Open Access without restrictions
- Contextualisation via indexing in specific databases, e.g. for OA books

Necessary

1. Access to the digital version of the publication is free and public immediately upon publication, without financial, legal or technical barriers.⁴ Editions that are subject to charge, such as a print edition, appear simultaneously or follow the OA version.
2. The publication is clearly labelled as an OA publication in all formats and editions.
3. The OA version of the publication is made available on the publisher’s/publication service’s website, if applicable together with additional versions offered for a fee.
4. The obligation to submit all published editions to the respective national libraries as well as to the respective state libraries is fulfilled.
5. Long-term archiving is carried out by an appropriately certified service.⁵
6. Text and data mining (TDM) is technically enabled and legally permitted. This includes the automatic downloading, extraction and indexing of the full texts and the associated metadata.

¹ Cf. <https://www.ag-univerlage.de>.

² Cf. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4622134>.

³ Original version: Arbeitsgemeinschaft der Universitätsverlage (2022). Qualitätsstandards für Open-Access-Bücher (Version 2), <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7075761>.

⁴ Accessibility also means implementing as best as possible the requirements of the Marrakesh Directive which is intended to achieve improved access to copyrighted works for the benefit of people with visual or reading disabilities, BGBl I, No. 40, p. 2014 (2018). Cf. https://www.bmj.de/SharedDocs/Gesetzgebungsverfahren/Dokumente/BGBl_Marrakesch-RiLi.pdf?__blob=publicationFile&v=2 (German). Retrieved July 7, 2022.

⁵ These can be services of the respective national libraries (e.g. <https://www.dnb.de/DE/Professionell/Erhalten/LZA-System/lza-system.html>), retrieved July 7, 2022) or of a central service provider such as CLOCKSS or Portico <https://www.portico.org/>. Services from larger institutions for the preservation of cultural heritage are also conceivable.

Recommended

7. Open access books are listed in corresponding databases (OAPEN and/or DOAB)⁶. In addition, the highest possible distribution and visibility is being aimed to achieve by providing evidence in other search portals such as BASE,⁷ subject databases and discovery services.
8. If book reviews are available, they will be listed.
9. Related research data and other materials are archived on a suitable repository and linked in the publication via a persistent identifier. The publication of research data should follow the FAIR principles and, if possible, be open access.

§ 2 Rights

Summary

- Strengthening of authors' rights
- Transparency and comprehensive re-use through OA compliant licensing

Necessary

1. Authors and editors grant the publisher/publication service simple rights of use and thus retain the right to grant rights of use to other parties and to publish the publication or parts thereof elsewhere.
2. The authors and editors grant the general public extensive rights of use by granting an Open Access-compliant Creative Commons licence (CC BY, CC BY-SA)⁸. Other, more restrictive licences that do not comply with the Berlin Declaration on Open Access to Knowledge in the Sciences and Humanities⁹ should be avoided.
3. The rights to illustrations and other third-party materials that are subject to third-party rights are clarified and clearly identified.
4. Rights and licence information are stored in the imprint and in the metadata of the files in a machine-readable form. It is available as a licence designation and as a link to the licence.

Recommended

5. Metadata and associated abstracts in all language versions are published under the CC0 1.0 Universal (CC0 1.0) licence, unless this is contrary to the form of publication (e.g. meeting abstracts).

§ 3 Quality Assurance

Summary

- Quality assurance ensures good scientific practice
- Transparency and traceability of quality assurance corresponds to Open Science

Necessary

1. The quality assurance measures of the publishing house/publication service are described transparently on the website.

⁶ Cf. <https://oapen.org/> and <https://doabooks.org/>.

⁷ Cf. <https://www.base-search.net/>.

⁸ Cf. <https://creativecommons.org/>.

⁹ Cf. <https://openaccess.mpg.de/Berliner-Erklaerung>, German version: Berliner Erklärung über den offenen Zugang zu wissenschaftlichem Wissen, <https://openaccess.mpg.de/68053/Berliner-Erklaerung-dt-Version-07-2006.pdf>. Retrieved July 21, 2022.

2. A peer review or review process is used for scientific examination that corresponds to subject-specific standards.
3. Established procedures to ensure good scientific practice before, during and after publication are set up; the relevant contact persons have been appointed

Recommended

4. The criteria and processes by which publications are selected and reviewed are described and publicly available. If committees carry out this selection and review, the committee members are named.
5. New, innovative forms of quality assurance that are oriented towards the requirements of science are supported.
6. Guidelines on publication ethics are formulated, integrated into the institution's own processes and transparently identified.

§ 4 Formats

Summary

- Permanent availability through suitable delivery formats
- Scientific and scholarly networking through digital, standardised and machine-readable information

Necessary

1. Publications are provided and archived in at least one digital file format suitable for long-term archiving.

Recommended

2. All digital editions contain, as far as technically possible, bookmarks and complete entries in the metadata (at least author, title, licence details).
3. Publications can also be distributed as a paid-for edition (e.g. print version).
4. The publisher/publication service aims to publish in structured and standardised formats that are suitable for (automatic) further processing and support accessibility.

§ 5 Metadata

Summary

- Metadata are essential elements of indexing
- Standardisation and networking of scientific information

Necessary

1. The metadata contain at least: title, additional title if applicable, author(s), publisher(s), licence information (e.g. Creative Commons licence), publication date, issuing body (e.g. publisher or publication service), persistent identifier (see § 6.1).

Recommended

2. Metadata should always be as comprehensive as possible. This includes abstracts; for periodicals such as series or yearbooks, periodicals title, volume number and ISSN; also ORCID iDs or other suitable persistent identifiers for persons, organisations as well as for publications and, if possible, affiliations, ISBN for parallel editions and keywords (free or taken from a classification).
3. The metadata, including abstracts, keywords and any thumbnails of the covers, are made available as freely as possible, ideally under the CC0 licence, assuming this does not conflict with the form of publication (e.g. meeting abstracts).

4. The affiliations of the authors and editors involved must be stated in accordance with the requirements of the applicable affiliation guidelines of the institutions. For this purpose, standardised specifications (e.g. ROR) are used.
5. Metadata are provided as CSV files, as ONIX XML feeds or in other established formats (Dublin Core, DataCite, Crossref). They are communicated via standardised interfaces and protocols.
6. The metadata are provided to the libraries as MARC records.

§ 6 Persistent Identifiers

Summary

- Promoting the potential of networking
- Deepening the development and transparency of promotion

Necessary

1. Each publication receives a persistent identifier, preferably a DOI. Other common identifiers are URN, EPIC, ARK or handle.
2. If research funders have made the OA publication possible, they are named in the document and, if applicable, in the metadata.

Recommended

3. Self-contained sub-units of a work are each given their own persistent identifier to ensure the citability of the sub-units.
4. Authors and editors are informed about the added value of the ORCID iD. If available, the ORCID iD is mentioned in the publication and integrated into the machine-readable metadata.
5. If publications are based on funded research, the information provided should be as comprehensive as possible (project, project title, project number, funding code, etc.). Where possible, standardised approaches (e.g. ROR or Crossref Funder Registry) should be used.

§ 7 Metrics

Summary

- Fair and comparable usage measurement

Recommended

1. The publisher/publication service should, wherever possible, provide services to fairly measure the usage of its publications and their citations.
2. Access figures are recorded and made available (on request if necessary), whereby the method used should be disclosed and comply with usual industry standards.

§ 8 Calculation

Summary

- Fairness towards sponsors and creators through comprehensible calculations
- OA and non-OA costs can be differentiated from each other

Necessary

1. If OA books are realized through public funding, the shares of OA-indexed costs must be differentiated from those of non-eligible items.

Recommended

2. Cost statements should be based on generally understandable production steps and service designations in order to enable comparability between offers.

§ 9 Communication

Summary

- Clear commitment of publishers and providers to Open Access
- Open Access conceived as joint process

Necessary

1. The publisher/publication service appoints a contact person for its OA program whom authors and editors can contact.
2. The publishing house/publication service provides information on the advantages of OA publication as well as on legal issues and OA licences.

Recommended

3. If advertising and marketing is carried out, it will be done on an equal basis for all editions via the publisher's/service's website, other media and via appropriate social media channels.

Editors: Ursula Arning, Margo Bargheer, Isabella Meinecke, Markus Putnings, Dagmar Schobert, Regine Tobias and Marco Winkler in the name of the AG Universitätsverlage.

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